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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated Troopers Ground's Suitability as a recreational spot in La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm of Iloilo State University of Fisheries Science and Technology (ISUFST) Dingle Campus. The respondents were 100 residents of the municipality in the province of Iloilo who were selected using a convenient sampling technique. Generally, the study revealed that Troopers Ground is highly suitable as a recreational spot in La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm of ISUFST Dingle Campus with a description of highly suitable. Mann-Whitney U test results showed a significant difference in the suitability level of Troopers' Ground regarding employment status. Results further implied that the suitability level of Troopers' Ground varies between employed and unemployed respondents.

On the other hand, no significant difference in the suitability level of Troopers' Ground regarding sex. Kruskal-Wallis H test results showed no significant differences in the suitability level of Troopers' Ground regarding age and educational qualifications. Results further implied that the suitability level of Troopers' Ground does not differ in age and employment status. The researcher recommends that the management of ISUFST Dingle Campus outsource and allocate the necessary budget for the construction and implementation of the Troopers' Ground, also to the Department of Tourism and Local Government Unit Dingle to outsource linkages and funding for the sustainability, marketing, and promotion of Troopers Ground after its construction.

Keywords: *Development Management, Agri-Ecotourism, Recreational Spot, Camping Site, Iloilo*

INTRODUCTION

The idea of Agri-Ecotourism as a potential tourist attraction may seem surprising. Bringing tourists to rural communities by combining agriculture and Ecotourism can improve the lives of small-scale farmers who have recently shifted from conventional to more sustainable farming methods (Kumar, 2019).

La Guerta is an Agri-Ecotourism Farm of a State University in the Fourth District of Iloilo - a 40.6 hectare of rolling hills - served as a venue for many seminars, workshops, and a training and assessment center for Technical Education and Skills Development Authority in Agricultural Crops Production National Certificate II and National Certificate III and Organic Agriculture Production National Certificate II. It has been progressively forging ahead in the implementation of scientific methods of farming and has spearheaded many government thrusts and programs.

La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm is the first school-based eco-farm in the Province of Iloilo, and it will offer educative. Moreover, interactive activities will include the following components: Animalville project will be a virtual educative and interactive sustainable enterprise. Activities on the farm will include skills training in animal raising for immersion and research tours and a feeding and petting activity for young and adult learners. Project Kandingan will be a goat milking activity that will teach the processing of products from goat's milk to adult learners. Project Coco will teach young and adult learners to make coco sugar, honey, candies, and virgin coconut oil. Project Karan-union will be a cooking-demo class for native Dingleanon delicacies, while Project Himukit will be an arts and craft activity for young and adult learners.

It was observed that there are no places to stay for backpacker tourists in a certain Municipality in the Fourth District of Iloilo. Aside from this, camping has been gaining popularity among nature lovers who wish to stay in the open field, experience stargazing, or explore nature.

This farm experience may also develop the love of young people for agricultural activities. This study evaluated the Suitability of Troopers' Ground as a Recreational Spot in La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm of a State University in the Fourth District of Iloilo.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study used the descriptive research design. According to Fraenkel et al. (2013), descriptive research design describes the status of people or subjects as they exist. The method that was used was a descriptive survey. This research design sought to help the Suitability of Troopers Ground as a recreational spot in La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm.

Participants/Respondents. The respondents of this study were 100 residents of a Municipality in the Fourth District of Iloilo, who were selected utilizing a convenient sampling technique.

Data Collection Procedure. The researcher secured an approved communication from the Office of the Municipal Mayor requesting permission to conduct the study. Once the permit was released, the researcher had a courtesy call to the Office of the Municipal Vice Mayor and Municipal Tourism Officer before distributing the research questionnaire. A self-made questionnaire checklist, validated by external experts, was prepared, and these were distributed to the 100 respondents, which were identified via convenient sampling techniques. The information acquired through data gathering with the respondents was subjected to the ranking system. After retrieving the accomplished instruments, the obtained data were encoded, tallied, and interpreted using the software.

Data Analysis Procedure. The researcher used mean, frequency, standard deviation, Mann-Whitney U Test, and Kruskal-Wallis H Test as the statistical treatment of this study. Frequency counts were used to determine the number of respondents belonging to a class or category of the independent variables. Means were used to determine Troopers Ground's Suitability as a recreational spot in La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm. Standard deviation was used to determine the dispersion of the mean as to its homogeneity or heterogeneity of scores. Mann-Whitney U Test was used to determine significant differences in the suitability level of Troopers' Ground when respondents were grouped as to sex and employment status. Kruskal-Wallis H Test was used to determine significant differences in the suitability level of Troopers' Ground when the respondents were grouped according to their age and educational qualifications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that out of 100 respondents, when grouped as to sex, 55.0% (55) were male, and 45.0% (45) were female. Moreover, when grouped as to age, 32.0% (32) were 20 years old and below, 45.0% (45) were 21 to 40 years old, and 23.0% (23) were 41 years old and above.

When grouped according to their educational qualifications, 6.0% (6) were elementary graduates, 24.0% (24) were high school graduates; college graduates were 56.0% (56), and 14.0% (14) were postgraduates.

Regarding employment status, 79.0% (79) were employed, and 21.0% (21) were unemployed.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Category	f	%
Entire Group	100	100.00
Sex		
Male	55	55.0
Female	45	45.0
Age		
20 years Old Below	32	32.0
21 to 40 years Old	45	45.0
41 years Old Above	23	23.0
Educational Qualifications		
Elementary Graduate	6	6.0
High School Graduate	24	24.0
College Graduate	56	56.0
Post Graduate	14	14.0
Employment Status		
Employed	79	79.0
Unemployed	21	21.0

Table 2 shows the suitability level of Troopers Ground when taken as a whole. Generally, the study revealed that Troopers Ground is highly suitable as a recreational spot in La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm of ISUFST Dingle Campus, with a mean of 4.87% and a description of highly suitable.

The respondents believed that Troopers Ground is an ideal location for recreational activities in La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm, with a mean of 4.85, which is highly suitable.

Item no. 2 refers to the availability of facilities available in Troopers Ground that are adequate for the recreational needs of visitors. This obtained a mean of 4.84 which is highly suitable.

According to the respondents, Troopers Ground has a welcoming atmosphere that encourages visitors to engage in recreational activities with 4.80, and it is highly suitable, as stated in item no. 3.

The respondents also believed that the maintenance of Troopers Ground is sufficient to ensure the safety and comfort of visitors as stipulated in item no. 4, with a 4.82 mean and a highly suitable description. In item no. 5, respondents believed that Troopers Ground's location enhances visitors' overall experience of La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm with a mean of 4.83 and highly suitable as its description.

Respondents also believed that Troopers Ground is easily accessible to visitors of all ages and physical abilities, with a mean of 4.88, with highly suitable as its description as stated in item no. 6.

Item no. 7 had a mean of 4.83, which is highly suitable. It refers to the variety of recreational activities available in Troopers Ground that cater to visitors' diverse needs and interests.

Item no. 8 garnered a mean of 4.84 and had a highly suitable description, which refers if the staff at Troopers Ground are helpful and knowledgeable about the recreational activities and facilities available.

On the other hand, items 9 and 10 got a mean of 4.90 and a highly suitable description, respectively.

The overall experience of visiting Troopers Ground is enjoyable and worthwhile, as stated in item no. 11, garnered a 4.80 mean and a highly suitable description.

Respondents further believed that the recreational activities available in Troopers Ground are unique and memorable, as stated in item no. 12, which obtained a mean of 4.84 and a description of highly suitable.

Item no. 13, which refers to the natural environment surrounding Troopers Ground which adds to the overall appeal of the recreational area, had a mean of 4.90, highly suitable as its description.

Respondents also believed that the safety measures at Troopers Ground are adequate for the various recreational activities offered, with a mean of 4.89 and a description of highly suitable, as stated in item no. 14.

Item no. 15 had a mean of 4.90 with a highly suitable description, which refers to the Troopers Ground staff being friendly and approachable.

Moreover, item no. 16 had a mean of 4.86 highly suitable, referring to Troopers Ground as a suitable location for families with young children.

Item no. 17, which states that the recreational activities offered at Troopers Ground promote physical fitness and well-being, had a mean of 4.89 and a highly suitable description.

With item no. 18, respondents further believed that the layout and design of Troopers Ground are well-suited to the recreational activities offered, which garnered a mean of 4.91 and a highly suitable description.

A mean of 4.91 with a highly suitable description was obtained by item no. 19, which refers to adequate refreshments and food availability at Troopers Ground

Item no. 20, which refers if Troopers Ground, offers a unique and immersive experience for visitors to La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm, obtained a mean of 4.93 with a highly suitable description.

Table 2. Suitability Level of Troopers Ground as a Whole

	Mean	SD	Description
1. Troopers Ground is an ideal location for recreational activities in La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm.	4.85	.359	Highly Suitable
2. The facilities available in Troopers Ground are adequate for the recreational needs of visitors.	4.84	.368	Highly Suitable
3. Troopers Ground has a welcoming atmosphere that encourages visitors to engage in recreational activities.	4.80	.426	Highly Suitable
4. The maintenance of Troopers Ground is sufficient to ensure the safety and comfort of visitors.	4.82	.386	Highly Suitable
5. Troopers Ground's location enhances visitors' overall experience of La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm.	4.83	.403	Highly Suitable
6. Troopers Ground is easily accessible to visitors of all ages and physical abilities.	4.88	.327	Highly Suitable
7. The variety of recreational activities available in Troopers Ground caters to visitors' diverse needs and interests.	4.83	.403	Highly Suitable
8. The staff at Troopers Ground are helpful and knowledgeable about the recreational activities and facilities available.	4.84	.420	Highly Suitable
9. The cost of participating in recreational activities at Troopers Ground is reasonable and affordable.	4.90	.333	Highly Suitable
10. The cleanliness of Troopers Ground is well-maintained.	4.90	.302	Highly Suitable
11. The overall experience of visiting Troopers Ground is enjoyable and worthwhile.	4.80	.471	Highly Suitable
12. The recreational activities available in Troopers Ground are unique and memorable.	4.84	.368	Highly Suitable
13. The natural environment surrounding Troopers Ground adds to the overall appeal of the recreational area.	4.90	.302	Highly Suitable
14. The safety measures in place at Troopers Ground are adequate for the various recreational activities offered.	4.89	.345	Highly Suitable
15. The staff at Troopers Ground are friendly and approachable.	4.90	.302	Highly Suitable
16. Troopers Ground is a suitable location for families with young children.	4.86	.377	Highly Suitable
17. The recreational activities offered at Troopers Ground promote physical fitness and well-being.	4.89	.314	Highly Suitable
18. The layout and design of Troopers Ground are well-suited to the recreational activities offered.	4.91	.288	Highly Suitable
19. The availability of refreshments and food at Troopers Ground is adequate.	4.91	.288	Highly Suitable
20. Troopers Ground offers a unique and immersive experience for visitors to La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm.	4.93	.256	Highly Suitable
CM=	4.87	.217	Highly Suitable

Table 3 shows the suitability level of Troopers' Ground as a whole as to variables. When taken as an entire group, the mean was 4.47, and a highly suitable description.

When categorized as sex, the males got a 4.87 mean while the females got a 4.85 mean; both had a highly suitable description.

When a group as to age, 20 years old and below had a mean of 4.87, 21 to 40 years old had a mean of 4.88, and 41 years old and above had a 4.82 mean. All are highly suitable in terms of their description.

If the respondents were categorized as educational qualifications, elementary graduates had a mean of 4.92, and respondents who were high school graduates obtained a mean of 4.78. On the other hand, respondents who were college graduates obtained a mean of 4.91, while postgraduate respondents had a mean of 4.82. All had a highly suitable description.

When grouped according to employment status, respondents who were employed had a mean of 4.90, and those who were unemployed had a 4.75 mean. All had a highly suitable description.

Table 3. Suitability Level of Troopers' Ground as a Whole as to Variables

Category	Mean	SD	Description
<i>Entire Group</i>	4.87	.217	Highly Suitable
<i>Sex</i>			
Male	4.87	.220	Highly Suitable
Female	4.85	.215	Highly Suitable
<i>Age</i>			
20 years Old Below	4.87	.222	Highly Suitable
21 to 40 years Old	4.88	.180	Highly Suitable
41 years Old Above	4.82	.276	Highly Suitable
<i>Educational Qualifications</i>			
Elementary Graduate	4.92	.204	Highly Suitable
High School Graduate	4.78	.290	Highly Suitable
College Graduate	4.91	.169	Highly Suitable
Post Graduate	4.82	.219	Highly Suitable
<i>Employment Status</i>			
Employed	4.90	.177	Highly Suitable
Unemployed	4.75	.307	Highly Suitable

Mann-Whitney U test results showed a significant difference in the suitability level of troopers' ground as to employment status [U = 624.50; p=.040]. The two-tailed probability of .040 is greater than the set alpha level of .05. Results further implied that the suitability level of troopers' ground varies between employed and unemployed respondents. On the other hand, no significant difference in the suitability level of troopers' ground as to sex [U = 1118.00; p=.327].

Table 4

Differences in the Suitability Level of Troopers Ground as to Sex and Employment Status

Compared Means	Mean Rank	Uvalue	Sig.	Interpretation
<i>Sex</i>				
Male	52.67	1118.00	.327	Not Significant
Female	47.84			
<i>Employment Status</i>				
Employed	53.09	624.50*	.040	Significant
Unemployed	40.74			

Kruskal-Wallis H test results showed no significant differences in the suitability level of troopers' ground as to age [$H_{(2)}=.300$; $p=.861$] and educational qualifications [$H_{(3)}=6.517$; $p=.080$]. The two-tailed probabilities of .861 and .089 are greater than the set alpha level of .05. Results further implied that the suitability level of troopers' ground does not differ in age and employment status.

Table 5
Differences in the Suitability Level of Troopers Ground as to Age and Educational Qualifications

Sources of Variations	df	Mean Rank	H _{value}	Sig. (2-tailed)	Interpretation
Age					
20 years Old Below	2	51.55	.300	.861	Significant
21 to 40 years Old		50.99			
41 years Old Above		48.09			
Educational Qualifications					
Elementary Graduate	3	57.75	6.517	.089	Not Significant
High School Graduate		41.44			
College Graduate		55.04			
Post Graduate		44.75			

CONCLUSION

Based on the study's findings, the researcher can conclude that the suitability level of Troopers' Ground as a recreational spot in La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm is highly suitable.

The researcher also concludes that the management of La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm should adopt the proposed business plan attached to this study.

Moreover, the researcher further concludes that residents in the component municipality in the fourth district of Iloilo, nowadays were fully aware of the existence of La Guerta Agri-Ecotourism Farm and that they were looking forward to the entire operation of Troopers' Ground since there is an absence of this recreational spot and accommodation facility in the town.

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Declaration of Conflicting Interest. There are no conflicts concerning this research paper, authorship, and publication.

Funding. No funding from external sources, such as donations or grants, was received for conducting research, authorship, and publication of this paper.